

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF SELF EFFICACY AMONG HINDU AND MUSLIM STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT:

The present study objective at assessing the comparative analysis of self-efficacy among Hindu and Muslim students Ranchi. The sample of the study consists of 100 subjects classified as 50 Hindu and 50 Muslim (all females) were selected randomly. The entire Sample Was collected from Nirmala college. The tools were used to achieve the goal of present study Personal Data Questionnaire and Manual of Self efficacy scale. The result revealed that student academic self-efficacy affects student satisfaction but only indirectly, by fulfilling the latent variable expectancy value beliefs.

KEYWORDS:

SELF-EFFICACY, OUTCOME EXPECTANCY, MOTIVATION, PERCEIVED CAPABILITY, HEALTH BEHAVIOR THEORY.

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INTRODUCTION

Self-efficacy is a set of beliefs that influence the decisions individuals make and the subsequent actions they choose to carry out. Researchers have argued that how people behave and what they will achieve can often be better predicted by the beliefs they hold about their own capabilities than by what they are actually capable of accomplishing. This resource provides a brief overview of the concept of self-efficacy and its importance for teachers and students.

In the 1970s, psychologist Albert Bandura developed the framework of self-efficacy, and it has been widely used in the field of education over the past three decades. Bandura defined self-efficacy as the 'belief in one's capabilities to organize and execute the courses of action required to attain designated types of performances. He argued that people with high self-efficacy will apply effort, persevere and demonstrate resilience when faced with challenging tasks, while those with low self-efficacy tend to hold back during difficult tasks, expect mediocre results, and give up easily. Self-efficacy judgements affect which activities individuals choose or avoid, how much effort they put in, how much resilience they have, and how long they persist with a task. People with high self-efficacy enjoy challenges and respond proactively to failure. They set higher goals and expend more effort towards their achievement. They are more self-regulating, persist longer and use more cognitive and metacognitive strategies (higher level thinking), showing an understanding of what is involved to carry out a task successfully. People with low self-efficacy are more likely to avoid difficult tasks and have low commitment to goals.

1.1 DEFINATION

The term self-efficacy refers to an individual's confidence in their ability to complete a task or achieve a goal. The concept was originally developed by Albert Bandura. Today, psychologists Contend that our sense of self-efficacy can influence whether we actually succeed at a task. Self-efficacy refers to the set of beliefs we hold about our ability to complete a particular task.

According to psychologist Albert Bandura, the first proponent of the concept, self-efficacy cy is the product of past experience, observation, persuasion, and emotion. Self-efficacy is linked to academic achievement and the ability to overcome phobias. Self-efficacy has important effects on the amount of effort individuals apply to a given task. Someone with high levels of self-efficacy for a given task will be resilient and persistent in the face of setbacks, while someone with low levels of self-efficacy for that task may disengage or avoid the situation. For example, a student who has a lower level of self-efficacy for math might avoid signing up for challenging math classes. In other words, our ability to achieve a goal or complete a task depends on whether we think we can do it (self-efficacy), and whether we think it will have good results (outcome expectancy).

1.2 THE IMPORTANCE OF SELF- EFFICACY

According to Bandura, there are two factors that influence whether or not someone engages in a particular behavior: outcome expectancy and self-efficacy.

Importantly, our level of self-efficacy varies from one domain to the next. For example, you might have high levels of self-efficacy about your ability to navigate your hometown, but have very low levels of self-efficacy about

your ability to navigate a foreign city where you do individual's level of self-efficacy for one task not speak the language.

Generally, an cannot be used to predict their self-efficacy for another task. Self-efficacy can greatly impact how people feel, think, behave, and motivate themselves. People who have a heightened sense of self-efficacy: See challenging problems as tasks to be mastered, rather than threats to be avoided. Develop greater intrinsic interest and focus in their activities. Set challenging goals and demonstrate a stronger sense of commitment to them. Quickly recover their self-efficacy following setbacks and disappointments (Bandura, 1994).

PEOPLE WHO HAVE A LOW SENSE OF SELF-EFFICACY:

Avoid difficult tasks and view them as personal threats. Have a weak commitment to their goals and believe that difficult tasks and situations are beyond their capabilities. Dwell on personal failings and negative outcomes, rather than how to succeed. Quickly lose faith in their personal abilities and easily develop depression and stress (Bandura, 1994).

In addition, people who possess high self-efficacy have a tendency to learn and achieve more than those with low self-efficacy, "even when actual ability levels are the same" (Ormrod, 2008, p. 137).

1.3 COMPONENTS

Scholars have found four sources of information that people use to judge their efficacy: performance outcomes, vicarious experiences, verbal persuasion, and physiological feedback (Bandura 1977; Gist & Mitchell, 1992; as cited in Redmond, 2010).

These components help individuals determine they believe they have the capability to accomplish certain tasks. Based on research of the four sources, performance outcomes are the most effective in influencing self-efficacy since they are derived from personal experiences (Redmond, 2010).

Performance Outcomes - Positive and negative experiences can influence the ability of an individual to perform a given task. If one has performed well at a task previously, they are more likely to feel competent and perform well at a related task (Redmond, 2010). For example, if one performed well in a training workshop, they are more likely to feel confident and have high self-efficacy in another training workshop. The individual's self-efficacy will be high in that given area, and since he/she has a high self-efficacy, he/she is more likely to try harder and complete the task with much better results. Vice versa, previously failed tasks will result in low self-efficacy (Redmond, 2010).

Vicarious Experiences -People can develop high or low

self-efficacy vicariously through other people's performances. A person can watch another perform and then compare their competence with the other's competence (Redmond, 2010). If a person sees someone similar to them succeed, it can increase their self-efficacy.

However, the opposite is also true; seeing someone similar fail can lower self-efficacy. An example of how vicarious experiences can increase self-efficacy in the work place is through mentoring programs, where an individual can be paired with someone on a similar career path who is successful at raising the individual's self-efficacy beliefs. An example of how the opposite can be true is in a smoking cessation program where if one or two people fail to quit, another person's efficacy belief can be lowered, hence he/she may also fail to quit.

Verbal Persuasion -According to Redmond (2010), self-efficacy is also influenced by encouragement and discouragement pertaining to an individual's performance or ability to perform; such as a manager telling an employee, "You can do it, I have confidence in you." Using verbal persuasion in a positive light leads individuals to put forth more effort; therefore, they have a greater chance at succeeding. However, if the verbal persuasion is negative, such as a manager saying to the employee, "This is unacceptable! I thought you could handle this project" can lead to doubts about oneself resulting in lower chances of success. Also, the effectiveness of verbal persuasion is directly influenced by the level of credibility; where there is more credibility there will be a greater influence. In the example above, a pep talks by a manager who has an established, respectable position would have a stronger influence than that of a newly hired manager.

Physiological Feedback - People experience sensations from their body and how they perceive these emotional arousals influences their beliefs of efficacy (Redmond, 2010). Some examples of physiological feedback are: giving a speech in front of a large group of people, making a presentation to an important client, taking an exam, etc. All of these tasks can cause agitation, anxiety, sweaty palms, and/or a racing heart (Redmond, 2010). Although this source is the least influential of the four, it is important to note capable and have higher beliefs of self-efficacy. that if one is more at ease with the task at hand, they will feel more capable and have higher beliefs of self-efficacy.

1.4 CHARACTERSTICS

1. THE CHARACTERISTICS OF LOW SELF-EFFICACY:

A) Fear of risks Individuals with low self-efficacy see themselves as unable to be successful. As a result, they are often unwilling to take risks or try new things because they are convinced that the result will be failure. This is particularly unfortunate because the main way to increase self-efficacy is through practice and experience.

B) Fear of uncertainty. Low self-efficacy often is related to self-doubt and uncertainty. The individual doesn't want to try without a guarantee of success. As a result, they may

never discover things at which they could be successful.

C) Feelings of failure. Those with low self-efficacy frequently have feelings of failure. As indicated above they might avoid or not try new things due to the risk involved. Or, they might only try something half-heartedly. As a result, they are less likely to experience success and more likely to see themselves as a failure.

D) Impression management.

Impression management is the attempt to control how others might perceive you in order to be seen more positively. People with low self-efficacy feel they are not capable but may try to present a successful and competent image to others. They may put a great deal of energy into behaving in a way to obtain approval from others and experience a great deal of worry about being found out to be a fraud. For instance, they may try to hide mistakes from others rather than learn from them which prevents them from increasing their sense of self-efficacy.

2. THE CHARACTERISTICS OF HIGH SELF-EFFICACY:

A) Self-confidence.

One of the most obvious characteristics of high self-efficacy is self-confidence. They approach tasks or situations with a sense of their ability to be successful. This self-confidence tends to lead to more experience which increases their ability which leads to greater self-confidence. This positive cycle lends itself to increasing self-efficacy even further.

B) Accurate self-evaluation.

Individuals with high self-efficacy tend to be able to accurately evaluate their performance. They are neither overly critical nor overly positive but are able to examine themselves realistically in order to pursue self-improvement.

C) Willingness to take risks.

Those with high self-efficacy are willing to take risks because they understand that taking calculated risks increases the chances of success. As they are not fearful of failure or mistakes, reasonable risks can only increase self-efficacy.

D) Sense of accomplishment.

Generally, those with high self-efficacy feel a sense of accomplishment because they are often more successful due to the willingness to take risk and to pursue interests. Even if they fail or make mistakes, they feel a sense of accomplishment because they view mistakes as opportunities to improve themselves.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Today there is a huge need for a scientific literature review especially for researchers who are preparing research proposals. Scientific journals are mostly filled with research results that are proof of the theory. There are not many articles that contain a literature review on an actual

issue. This essay aims to present a concise literature review of self-efficacy. The discussion focused on exploring the basic theories, definitions, dimensions, sources, roles, and antecedents and consequences of self-efficacy. This paper is expected to contribute especially to researchers who are preparing research proposals on this issue.

The purpose of this review was threefold. First, the theorized sources of self-efficacy beliefs proposed by A. **Bandura (1986)** are described and explained, including how they are typically assessed and analyzed. Second, findings from investigations of these sources in academic contexts are reviewed and critiqued, and problems and oversights in current research and in conceptualizations of the sources are identified. Although mastery experience is typically the most influential source of self-efficacy, the strength and influence of the sources differ as a function of contextual factors such as gender, ethnicity, academic ability, and academic domain. Finally, suggestions are offered to help guide researchers investigating the psychological mechanisms at work in the formation of self-efficacy beliefs in academic contexts.

Researchers and practitioners in the field of second language acquisition have come to realize the importance of non-cognitive skills such as self-efficacy and self-regulation in students' learning of a second language. However, there has been limited systematic research on such measures in the second language context and the validity and reliability of their intended use and interpretation. The Questionnaire of English Self-Efficacy (QESE) was designed to measure English language learners' self-efficacy beliefs. This study applied the Rasch model to evaluate the item-level psychometric properties of QESE and its adequacy for use in the Vietnamese context. The results demonstrated that the QESE items predominantly measured a unidimensional construct (i.e., self-efficacy beliefs in learning English as a second language). The scale was highly reliable, and its rating categories functioned effectively, reflecting varying levels of self-efficacy beliefs. Although the item difficulty hierarchical order was generally consistent with the anticipated hierarchy within the Vietnamese context, there were a few surprising results, contradicting what was previously found with Chinese students. For example, item 28 (writing diaries in English) was a very difficult task for Vietnamese students, but a previous study showed that it was a moderately difficult task for Chinese students. Item 5 (writing blogs on the internet) was an easy task for Vietnamese students, but it was a difficult task for Chinese students. The findings provide directions for future research and have implications for helping professionals provide best practices that meet the unique educational needs of English language learners. Abstract Researchers and practitioners in the field of second language acquisition have come to realize.

In recent years, information and communication technologies have become relevant in both language learning and language education. This paper shows how online tools are applied in EFL vocational training at a

state school in Valencia, Spain. We present a technology-focused project carried out in the academic year 2017-2018 with students on the course "Business English." This project aimed to help these learners improve written competence through blogging. This experiment was carried out within the project-based learning approach. Our main purpose is to shed light on blogging within the PBL approach in the English for specific purposes course by answering this question: Can technology improve foreign language learning in both formal and face-to-face education in vocational training? Our final objective, based on the outcomes of this experiment, is to offer ideas for future best teaching practices so that other teaching professionals can also implement blogging in their classrooms; not only in their face-to-face training courses but also in distance education as well as blended education. For this purpose, we propose paying special attention to the following features: collaborative learning and team learning.

Self-efficacy is central to health behaviors theories due to its robust predictive capabilities. In this paper we present and review evidence for a self-efficacy-as-motivation argument which standard self-efficacy cy questionnaires-i.e., ratings of whether participants "can do" the target behaviors-reflect motivation rather than perceived capability. The potential implication is that associations between self-efficacy ratings (particularly those that employ a "can do" operationalization) and health-related behaviors simply indicate that people are likely to do what they are motivated to do. There is some empirical evidence for the self-efficacy-as-motivation argument, with three studies demonstrating causal effects of outcome expectancy on subsequent self-efficacy ratings. Three additional studies show that consistent with the self-efficacy-as-motivation argument-controlling for motivation by adding the phrase "if you wanted to" to the end of self-efficacy items decreases associations between self-efficacy ratings and motivation. Likewise, a qualitative study using a thought listing procedure demonstrates that self-efficacy ratings have motivational antecedents. The available evidence suggests that the self-efficacy-as-motivation argument is viable, although more research is needed. Meanwhile, we recommend that researchers look beyond self-efficacy to identify the many and diverse sources of motivation for health-related behaviors.

Self-efficacy-defined as perceived capability to perform a target behaviour (Bandura, 1977, 1986, 1997, 2004) is a robust predictor of various health behavior's (Armitage & Conner, 2001; Godin & Kok, 1996), including physical activity (Bauman et al., 2012), healthy eating (Abusabha & Achterberg, 1997), smoking cessation (Gwaltney, Metrik, Kahler, & Shiffman, 2009), alcohol abstinence (Adamson, Sellman, & Frampton, 2009), health behaviour change among cancer survivors (Park & Gaffey, 2007), and general health outcomes (Holden, 1991), Self-efficacy is the primary explanatory construct in Bandura's (1986, 1997) social cognitive 13 Scanned

theory-one of the most often used health behaviour theories (HBTS) (Glanz & Bishop, 2010)-and is included in several other often-used HBTS, including protection motivation theory (Rogers, 1983), the health belief model (Rosenstock, Strecher, & Becker, 1988), and the transtheoretical model (Prochaska & DiClemente, 1983). Additionally, perceived behavioural control in the theory of planned behaviour is defined and operationalized in ways that are similar to self-efficacy (Ajzen, 1991, 2002). Thus, the concept of self-efficacy is pervasive in health behaviors science.

One of the purported strengths of self-efficacy is that it explains why people are (or are not) motivated to perform health-related behavior's, rather than merely predicting who is (or is not) motivated to perform health-related behaviors. Specifically, according to self-efficacy theory (a component of social cognitive theory that emphasizes the role of self-efficacy; Bandura, 1997), self-efficacy is positioned early in a causal chain of factors that are posited to determine behaviour. Self-efficacy influences behaviour directly and through its effects on expected outcomes of the behaviour, the setting of relevant and challenging goals, and perceived barriers to and facilitators of the target.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF SELF EFFICACY AMONG HINDU AND MUSLIM STUDENTS OF NIRMALA COLLEGE RANCHI.

OBJECTIVE:

- I. To find out the level of self-efficacy of Hindu and Muslim students of Nirmala collage of Ranchi.
- ii To find out difference between Hindu and Muslim students in their self-efficacy.

HYPOTHESIS:

- The level of self-efficacy will be differed in the Hindu and Muslim students.
- There will be significance difference between the Hindu and Muslim students.

SAMPLE:

The sample of the study consists of 100 subjects classified as fifty Hindu and fifty Muslim (all females) were selected randomly. The entire sample was collected from Nirmala College. Their age is from 18-20 years.

TOOLS

The following tools were used to achieve the goal of present story.

- a. Personal data questionaries.
- b. Manual of self-efficacy scale 16

PERSONAL DATA QUESTIONARIES

The questionaries were prepared by researchers for

collecting information about the respondents name, age, ethnicity, caste, religion, gender, economic status etc;

SELF-EFFICACY SCALE

The General Self-Efficacy Scale is a 10-item psychometric scale that is designed to assess optimistic self-beliefs to cope with a variety of difficult demands in life. The scale has been originally developed in German by Matthias Jerusalem and Ralf Schwarzer in 1981 and has been used in many studies with hundred thousand of participants. In contrast to other scales that were designed to assess optimism, this one explicitly refers to personal agency, i.e., the belief that one's actions are responsible for successful outcomes. Perceived self-efficacy is a prospective and operative construct.

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

This scale is based on the original scales created by **Bandura (1990)** and by **Pastorelli et al. (2001)**. This scale was used to assess students' self-perception of how competent they were in the academic field. Students indicated their level of agreement within the 1 (very bad) to 4 (very good) range.

About: This scale is a self-report measure of self-efficacy. Items: 10 Reliability: Internal reliability for GSE = Cronbach's alphas between .76 and .90 Validity: The General Self-Efficacy Scale is correlated to emotion, optimism, work, satisfaction. Negative coefficients were found for depression, stress, health complaints, burnout and anxiety.

Scoring:

All Questions	Not at all true	Hardly true	Moderately true	Exactly true
	1	2	3	4

The total score is calculated by finding the sum of all items. For the GSE, the total score ranges between 10 and 40, with a higher score indicating more self-efficacy.

DISCUSSION

Based on a socio-cognitive perspective of motivation, this study examines; first, the mediator role played by expectancy-value beliefs in the relationship between students' academic self-efficacy and student achievement; second, the mediator role played by expectancy-value beliefs in the relationship between students' academic self-efficacy and student satisfaction with the teaching process. Achievement and satisfaction were considered dependent variables in two separate models as indicators of teaching practice quality.

For the mediator role played by the expectancy-value beliefs in the relationship between students' academic self-efficacy and student achievement, and following the recommendation by **Baron and Kenny (1986)** for testing mediation, the prediction capacity of students' academic self-efficacy on student achievement was examined first by testing the M1A model; second the mediator role played by expectancy-value beliefs in the relationship between students' academic self-efficacy and student achievement

was examined by testing the M2A model. According to the MIA model, the structural analyses indicated a direct, positive and significant effect of the latent variable academic self-efficacy on achievement. According to the M2A model, the obtained fit indices supported the hypothesized connections. This means that the expectancy-value beliefs mediated the relationship between students' academic self-efficacy and student achievement. These results indicated that students' academic self-efficacy affects student achievement, but only indirectly; i.e., by fulfilling the latent variable expectancy-value beliefs.

For the mediator role played by expectancy-value beliefs in the relationship between students' academic self-efficacy and student satisfaction with the teaching process, and following the recommendation by **Baron and Kenny (1986)** for testing mediation, the prediction capacity of students' academic self-efficacy on student satisfaction was examined 20 Scarned with CarnScamer first by testing the M1S model; second the mediator role played by expectancy-value beliefs in the relationship between students' academic self-efficacy and student satisfaction was examined by testing the M2S model.

In accordance with the M1S model, the structural analyses indicated a positive and significant direct effect of students' academic self-efficacy on the latent variable teaching process. According to the M2S model, the obtained fit indices supported the hypothesized connections. This means that the expectancy-value beliefs mediated the relationship between students' academic self-efficacy and student satisfaction. These results suggested that students' academic self-efficacy affects student satisfaction, but only indirectly; i.e., by fulfilling the latent variable expectancy-value beliefs.

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